

**EVALUATION OF DEVELOPMENT TRENDS OF AGRO-TOURISM OF
"NAMANGAN REGION REGIONS"**

Musaxanov Qazixon Abdulxakim o'g'li

Independent researcher of Namangan Institute of Engineering and Technology.

Phone: +998930524271

Email: мусакхановқозикҳон@змаил.ком

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10969526>

Abstract. *The statistical analysis of the processes taking place in agrotourism in the modern tourism industry is aimed at the development of economic forecasts for the assessment of the development trends of agrotourism for the near future.*

Keywords: *Agrotourism, Modern tourism, statistics, agrotourism services, agrotourism products, agrotourism trends.*

**ОЦЕНКА ТЕНДЕНЦИЙ РАЗВИТИЯ АГРОТУРИЗМА
«РЕГИОНОВ НАМАНГАНСКОЙ ОБЛАСТИ»**

Аннотация. *Статистический анализ процессов, происходящих в агротуризме в современной туристической отрасли, направлен на разработку экономических прогнозов для оценки тенденций развития агротуризма на ближайшую перспективу.*

Ключевые слова: *Агротуризм, Современный туризм, статистика, агротуристические услуги, агротуристические продукты, тенденции агротуризма.*

In the conditions of constant changes in the modern world, statistical analysis of the studied events and processes taking place in agrotourism is of particular importance. The development of economic forecasts for the development of agritourism for the near future has become especially difficult in the conditions of constant uncertainty and known inaccuracy of statistical data. In this regard, the information collected by the cell is very important.

Modern tourism industry is one of the largest, most profitable and dynamic industries in the world. Tourism accounts for about 10% of world GDP, world investment, all jobs and world consumption. According to the World Tourism Organization, in the last ten years, the number of tourists from tourism has increased by 7.9 percent per year, and the number of incoming tourists by 4.5 percent per year. European tourism appeared in the early 70s of the last century. At that time, many large cities have ecological issues, and people need to have healthy food, healthy food, and healthy food.

Today, tourism is developing rapidly, and in some countries, the flow of foreign tourists is drawing a part of it. Countries such as Italy, France, and Ireland can be cited as examples. The term "agritourism" is self-inflicted. It was the täää täää of the traditional tättä household. Agrarian tourism is determined by modern associations for its development. Thus, the International Economic Development Association (IED) gives the following interpretation. Agrotourism is a complex tourist product of the tourism industry directed to the creation of the village's natural, cultural, historical and other resources to use and its unique characteristics. Agrotourism association is defined as: agrotourism - agrotourism is an organization of activities in which accommodation, accommodation, food, excursion services, all-time organization and dispute resolution, complex services are formed and visitors are invited to visit. korzadastogan svetsya,

active seat of tourism tourism, fishing, hunting, acquisition of knowledge and skills. According to the association, agrotourism is aimed at creating a complex tourist product from the agricultural, natural, cultural-historical and other resources of the rural area and its specific features.

The development of economic forecasts for the development of agrotourism in the regions of Namangan region has become especially relevant in the conditions of constant uncertainty and a certain lack of statistical data. In this regard, forward-looking information is very important.

Forecasting is the modeling of the real situation, its implementation in the abstract field with the verification of the final results and the analysis of the progress of a certain forecasted situation, and forecasting is an integral part of the management process. This is especially true in the field of economic events, where the outcome of today's decisions largely depends on what will happen tomorrow.

Forecasting reduces uncertainty and helps to increase the accuracy of the decision, thereby eliminating the losses of economic entities. Therefore, one of the tasks of the research is to forecast the development trends of agrotourism in the "Territory of Namangan Region". In order to forecast the indicators of the development of agrotourism activity, a trend analysis based on the calculation of the relative deviations of the indicated indicators from the level of the base period was conducted in the period of 2010-2022.

In this trend analysis, general statistical data of 2010-2022 of all family business enterprises operating in the field of agrotourism in the regions of Namangan region were selected.

The proposed "main statistical indicators

Indicators	2010	2015	2020	2021	2022	Change in 2022 compared to 2010 (+, -)
Number of visitors, people	3682	4170	4385	4379	4418	736
Average real income per capita, thousand soums	1,5	3,9	8,3	10,3	12,5	11
Type of services provided, in unit	9	11	17	18	20	11
Population of the city, thousand people	1529,7	1641,9	1857,5	1899,471	1943,9	414

If we pay attention to the data of the table, the number of visitors in the field of agrotourism and ecotourism was 3,682 in 2010, and by 2022 it increased by 736 to 4,418, which in turn increased the average income per capita of Namangan region by 11,000 soums 12. It reached 5 thousand som. By 2022, compared to 2010, the number of services provided by the "regions of Namangan region" agrotourism cluster has increased from 9 units to 20 types.

Using the dynamics of these indicators presented in the conducted studies, it is possible to perform an econometric analysis and forecast indicators in the future, these indicators are: the area of agricultural land allocated to each agrotourism in Namangan region; they include the size of agrotourism properties and the number of tourists using each agrotourism service.

It should be noted that we did not make any assumptions about the nature of the model, about the distribution of errors. Of course, many other complex (economic, social, political) factors (variables) that could increase the accuracy of the forecast were not taken into account in the calculated statistical forecast. This classic forecast model is based on data available for mathematical calculations from the history of time interval values and interpreted within a certain confidence interval. Therefore, such a forecast model is relatively simplified, but practical to show the main change in the trend in the short term. The conducted statistical trend analysis will help to better understand the forecast of agrotourism development in Namangan region, as well as the activities of the tourism sector in general. The scientific research carried out today allows to make more effective management decisions in the field of tourism, which largely depends on the outcome of tomorrow. Forecasting itself reduces uncertainty and helps increase decision accuracy.

Modern high-tech agricultural production based on international experience, scientific innovations and processes of integration of production structures of a specific direction greatly contribute to the development of tourism in rural areas.

Today, the cluster method is successfully used in the conditions of changing agriculture and adapting to environmental changes for sustainable innovative development in the agro-industrial complex. The formation of clusters in various sectors of the economy ensures innovation, regional self-organization and the growth of the competitiveness of the region.

REFERENCES

1. Nezdoyminov S.G. Cluster associations of entrepreneurs as a territorially productive form of optimization of the tourist and recreational economy of the Odesa region / S.G. Nezdoyminov // Scientific Bulletin. - Odesa State University of Economics. All-Ukrainian Association of Young Scientists. Sciences: economics, political science, history. - 2009. - No. 19(97). - pp. 53-65.
2. Protocol of 1995 to the Labor Inspection Convention, 1947 (Entry into force: 09 June 1998). NORMLEX Information System on International Labor Standards. <https://www.ilo.org/dyn/normlex/en/f?p=1000:12100>.
3. Data of the Namangan Region Statistics Department <http://www.namstat.uz/uz/>
4. Cassis, Y, Minogue, I 2005, Entrepreneurship in theory and history, Palgrave Macmillan, New York
5. Foss, K, Foss, NJ, Klein, PG, 2007, 'Original and derived judgment: an entrepreneurial theory of economic organization', Organization Studies, vol. 28, no. 12, pp. 1893-1912.
6. A. Yu. Aleksandrova. "International Tourism" - Moscow, 2017
7. A. S. Kuskov, V.L. Golubeva, T.N. Odintsova "Recreational Geography" Educational and Methodological Complex. - Saratov. 2018
8. Aleksandrova A.Yu "Geography tourism" teacher. Moscow 2018.
- 9 A.G. Granberg. Osnovy regionalnoy ekonomiki. Uchebnik. - M, 2016

10. Vorobeva O.A. Problemy prirodopolzovaniya i ustoychivogo razvitiya v recreatsionno-turisticheskoy sphere: monograph / O.A. Vorobeva, I.M. Dyshlovy, S.K. Kharichkov.: IPREED NAN Ukrainy, 2009. – 374 p.
11. Khromova A.V. Regional agrotourism product / ot idei do business plan: monograph. Kursk. South-Western State University. Kursk: OOO "Uchitel", 2014. 138 p
12. Bustonov M.M. Macroeconomic Trends and Patterns of Sustainable Economic Growth and its Quality// Test Engineering & Management. 2019. November-December. <http://www.testmagzine.biz/index.php/testmagzine/article/view/221>
13. Bustonov M.M. The Firm Aspects and conditions Providing the Qualities of Economic Growth in Uzbekistan //International Journal of Economic Theory and Application. 2017, 4(4): 32-39 <http://www.aascit.org/journal/archive2?journalId=918&paperId=4704>
14. Bustonov M.M., Ensuring Long-Term Economic Growth in the World and Econometric Analysis of Economic Growth of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the Context of Extensive, Intensive and Digital Economy. Miasto Przyszłości Kielce 2022, ISSN-L: 2544-980X. <https://miastoprzyszlosci.com.pl/index.php/mp/article/view/406>
15. Bustonov M.M., Analysis of Economic Growth in the Juglyar Cycle in World Countries. Web of Scholars: Multidimensional Research Journal (MRJ) Volume: 01 Issue: 03 | 2022 ISSN: (2751-7543) <http://innosci.org/index.php/wos/article/view/53/37>
16. Bustonov M.M. Digital Economy In Improving The Quality Of Economic Growth. European Journal of Molecular & Clinical Medicine ISSN 2515-8260 Volume 07, Issue 07, 2020.
17. Bustonov M.M. The firm aspects and conditions providing the qualities of economic growth in Uzbekistan. International Journal of Economic Theory and Application. 2017/ <http://www.aascit.org/journal/Ijeta>
18. Bustonov M.M. Macroeconomic Trends and Patterns of Sustainable Economic Growth and its Quality. // Test engineering & Management November-December 2019.
19. Bustonov M.M. Digital Economy In Improving The Quality Of Economic Growth. European Journal of Molecular & Clinical Medicine ISSN 2515-8260 Volume 07, Issue 07, 2020.
20. Bustonov M.M. The Firm Aspects and conditions Providing the Qualities of Economic Growth in Uzbekistan. International Journal of Economic Theory and Application. 2017/ <http://www.aascit.org/journal/Ijeta>
21. B. Baykhanov, Bustonov M.M. Econometric models of sectoral distribution of investments in the economy of Uzbekistan. SOUTH ASIAN Journal of Marketing and Management Research 2019
22. Bustonov M.M. Macroeconomic Trends and Patterns of Sustainable Economic Growth and its Quality. TEST ENGINEERING & MANAGEMENT Vol. 81: Nov/Dec 19 Publication Issue: Vol 81: Nov/Dec 19 Issue Publication Date: 31 December 2019 Published: 2019-11-22
23. Bustonov M.M.,Maxmudov B.J., Rakhimov B.I. Directions for improving the efficiency of the monitoring of commercial banks loan commitments. A Multidisciplinary Peer

- Reviewed Journal, Vol. 6 Issue 5, May 2020 Page No.: 304-310.
<http://journalnx.com/journalarticle/20151021>
24. Bustonov M.M.,Abdurakhmanova M. Organization of credit obligations and monitoring of commercial banks. ACADEMICIA An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal. ISSN: 2249-7137 Vol. 10 Issue 5, May 2020 Impact Factor: SJIF 2020 = 7.13
 25. Bustonov M.M.,Abdurakhmanova M. Main Directions of Improvement of the Process of Investment. International Journal on Integrated Education, Volume 3, Issue VI, June 2020 |18. e-ISSN : 2620 3502 p-ISSN : 2615 3785//
<http://journals.researchparks.org/index.php/IJIE/article/view/395>
 26. Bustonov M.M.,Maxmudov B.J., Rakhimov B.I. Basic concepts of the theory of uncertain sets and actions related to investment processes. International Engineering Journal For Research & Development. Vol. 5 No. 5 (2020): IEJRD, PUBLISHED: 2020-07-17
 27. Rakhimov B.I., Bustonov M.M. Determination of the level of risks in investment projects using econometric model. International Journal of Innovations in Engineering Research and Technology [ijiert] issn: 2394-3696 website: ijiert.org volume 7, issue 8, aug.-2020. Impact Factor: SJIF 2020 = 7.525
 28. Bustonov M.M.,Digital economy in improving the quality of economic growth. European Journal of Molecular & Clinical Medicine ISSN 2515-8260 Volume 07, Issue 07, 2020
 29. Bustonov M.M.,Maxmudov M., Improving Economic Mechanisms to Encourage Efficient Use of Industrial Production Power in Kashkadarya Region/ Annals of R.S.C.B., ISSN:1583-6258, Vol. 25, Issue 3, 2021, Pages. 8183 - 8196 Received 16 February 2021; Accepted 08 March 2021.
 30. Rakhimov B.I., Bustonov M.M. Analysis of monitoring and fulfillment of credit obligations in commercial banks/ International Journal of Business, Law, and Education Volume 02, Number 02, 2021. file:///C:/Users/admin/Desktop/16-Article%20Text-61-1-10-20210524%20(1).pdf
 31. Bustonov M.M.,Ensuring Long-Term Economic Growth in the World and Econometric Analysis of Economic Growth of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the Context of Extensive, Intensive and Digital Economy. Miasto Przyszłości ISSN-L:2544-980X Table of Content -Volume 26 (Aug 2022)
 32. Bustonov M.M., Analysis of Economic Growth in the Juglyar Cycle in World Countries. Vol. 1 No. 3 (2022): Web of Scholars : Multidimensional Research Journal Analysis of Economic Growth in the Juglyar Cycle in World Countries
 33. Bustonov M.M., Digitalization and Economic Growth. Miasto Przyszłości ISSN-L: 2544-980X Vol. 30 (2022): file:///C:/Users/Lenovo/Desktop/201-206+Digitalization+and+Economic+Growth.pdf
 34. Bustonov M.M., Implementation of the single complex cluster system in the territory of Uzbekistan. EURASIAN JOURNAL OF ACADEMIC RESEARCH Innovative Academy Research Support Center UIF = 8.1 | SJIF = 5.685 www.in-academy.uz Volume 2 Issue 13, December 2022 ISSN 2181-2020

35. Bustonov M.M., Economic growth: theoretical and practical aspect. EURASIAN JOURNAL OF ACADEMIC RESEARCH Innovative Academy Research Support Center UIF = 8.1 | SJIF = 5.685 www.in-academy.uz Volume 2 Issue 13, December 2022 ISSN
36. Bustonov M.M., Digital economy in improving the quality of economic growth. European Journal of Molecular & Clinical Medicine ISSN 2515-8260 Volume 07, Issue 07, 2020
37. Bustonov M.M., Maxmudov M., Improving Economic Mechanisms to Encourage Efficient Use of Industrial Production Power in Kashkadarya Region/ Annals of R.S.C.B., ISSN:1583-6258, Vol. 25, Issue 3, 2021, Pages. 8183 - 8196 Received 16 February 2021; Accepted 08 March 2021.
38. Bustonov M.M. Digital economy in improving the quality of economic growth// European Journal of Molecular & Clinical Medicine. ISSN 2515-8260 2020. Vol 07, Issue 07. <https://www.scopus.com/results/authorNamesList.uri?sort=count-f&src=SCOPUS>).
39. Bustonov M.M. Macroeconomic Trends and Patterns of Sustainable Economic Growth and its Quality// Test Engineering & Management. 2019. November-December. <http://www.testmagzine.biz/index.php/testmagzine/article/view/221>
40. Ishimbayev R.N. Criteria and principle of capability // Miasta Przyslosci 29, P 334-337
41. Ishimbayev R.N. Competitiveness of small business // Science and innovation. International scientific journal 1 (ISSUE 8), P 90-96
42. Ishimbayev R.N. CLASSIFICATION OF THE ASSESSMENT METHODS OF THE COMPETITIVENESS OF A SMALL BUSINESS // EURASIAN JOURNAL OF ACADEMIC RESEARCH 2 (Issue 13), P 1065-1070
43. Ishimbayev R.N. Ways to increase the competitiveness of enterprises // Central Asian Journal of Innovations on Tourism Management and Finance. (2023) Vol 1.4. P. 174-177
44. Ishimbayev R.N. Ways to Increase competitiveness of small enterprises and private enterprises in Uzbekistan // MIASTO PRZYSZŁOŚCI. (2023) Vol 1 P. 346-349.
45. Ishimbayev R.N. Critries and assessment of competitiveness of small business // Scientific and Technical Journal of Namangan Instituti of Engineering and Technology. (2022) Vol 7 P. 471-480
46. Ишимбаев Р.Н. Факторы, влияющие на развитие конкурентоспособности малого бизнеса и частного предпринимательства в Узбекистане. // Академические исследования в современной науке. 2022. Том 1. №19. С. 62-68
47. Ишимбаев Р.Н. Повышение конкурентоспособности малого бизнеса и частного предпринимательства. // Biznes-Эксперт журнал. №5 (185) 2023 стр 114-117
48. Ишимбаев Р.Н. Бизнес-экосистема как фактор повышения конкурентоспособности предприятия на рынке. // MIASTO PRZYSZŁOŚCI. (2022) Vol 30 P. 376-377.
49. Ишимбаев Р.Н. Методические подходы к оценке конкурентоспособности малого бизнеса. // Eurasian journal of law, finance and applied sciences Vol 2 Issue 12, November 2022
50. Ишимбаев Р.Н. Конкурентоспособность: понятие, значение и сущность. // Международный научно-образовательный электронные журнал «Образование и наука в XXI веке» 13.12.2022г №33 (том 4) стр 67-71

51. Ишимбаев Р.Н. Новые возможности организации и управлением предпринимательской деятельностью. // Globallashuv sharoitida tadbirkorlik va kichik biznesni rivojlantirishning dolzarb masalalari NamMTI 2022 yil 15-16 aprel 3-Том стр 237
52. Ишимбаев Р.Н. Проблемы развития бизнеса в Узбекистане в современных условиях. // "Yangi O'zbekiston iqtisodiyotini rivojlantirishning dolzarb masalalari" mavzusida Respublika miqyosidagi ilmiy-amaliy konferensiya NamMQI 29-30 сентябрь 2022 г. 2 часть стр 274-276
53. Ишимбаев Р.Н. Теоретический и практический анализ конкурентоспособности предприятий. // “Янги Ўзбекистон: Инновация, фан ва таълим” мавзусидаги республика 53-кўп тармоқли илмий масофавий онлайн конференция материаллари тўплами 30 июнь 2023 йил
54. Ишимбаев Р.Н. Классификация методов оценки конкурентоспособности малого бизнеса. // Андижон давлат университети ва Андижон машинасозлик институти “ERKIN BOZOR MECHANIZMLARINI JORIY ETISH HAMDA SOG’LOM RAQOBAT MUHITINI YARATISH ORQALI HUDUDLARDA TADBIRKORLIKNI RIVOJLANTIRISH ISTIQBOLLARI” mavzusida respublika miqyosidagi ilmiy-amaliy anjuman ILMIY MAQOLALAR VA TEZISLAR TO’PLAMI 4 mart 2023 yil
55. Ишимбаев Р.Н. Развитие рекламы в Республике Узбекистан и пути решения проблем. // "Ўзбекистон тadbirkor-бизнесменларини Евроосиё иқтисодий иттифиқининг товарлар ва хизматлар бозорларига мослашишларидаги маркетинг муаммолари" мавзусидаги халқаро анжумаи материллари ТЎПЛАМИ Тошкент 21.05.2022 стр 636